

Integration of Artificial Intelligence Techniques in Hearing Aid Technology: A Decade-long Literature Review (2015-2024)

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ABSTRACT

Background: Hearing aids have undergone a significant transformation in the last 10 years due to implementing artificial intelligence (AI) techniques, which not only improves sound processing, but also enables personalization and easier user experience. **Aim:** This literature review examines the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into hearing aid technology from 2015 to 2024, focusing on four core dimensions: technological foundations, clinical applications, demonstrated benefits, and implementation challenges. **Methodology:** A thematic analysis approach was employed to structure and synthesize the findings. **Results:** The findings reveal that AI, particularly through machine and deep learning, has significantly advanced hearing aid capabilities, enabling sophisticated environmental sound processing, adaptive noise reduction, and real-time speech enhancement. Modern devices now incorporate innovative features such as cognitive auditory processing, health monitoring, and user-specific personalization, moving beyond traditional amplification. There is a superior performance in speech clarity and noise suppression compared to conventional methods. However, persistent barriers—including hardware limitations, insufficient clinical validation, and user accessibility issues—hinder widespread adoption. **Conclusion:** A gap exists between laboratory efficacy and real-world performance, underscoring the need for practical implementation frameworks. Future advancements should prioritize energy-efficient processing, comprehensive training datasets, standardized evaluation protocols, human-centered design, and Interdisciplinary collaboration

Keywords: *Artificial intelligence, Hearing aids, Machine learning, Noise reduction, Speech enhancement.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) became an essential component of most assistive devices, which plays an important role in improving education and everyday activities among people with different disabilities through creation of simulated environments combined with augmented and virtual reality (Zdravkova et al., 2022). AI could be defined as the technology that empower machines or devices to accomplish tasks that need human intelligence (Frosolini et al., 2024) and it can simulate human behaviour (Fabry & Bhowmik, 2021). In the last decade the AI was widely employed to allow machines systems to learn from data and to predict or make decisions without a need for pre-programming, these abilities are known as Machine Learning (Frosolini et al., 2024). Improvement in the efficiency and accuracy of tasks performing bases on the accumulation of processed data by these systems (Frosolini et al., 2024).

In the last decade, there was a dramatic increase in potential benefits of AI to enhance health and wellbeing, assist in diagnosing, prevent illness, give

individualized therapy recommendations, and improved patients' outcomes (Frosolini et al., 2024; Wagan et al., 2022). This could refer to the wide availability of electronic medical records and increase using of computers to process patient's data (Wagan et al., 2022).

Recently, artificial intelligence (AI) was integrated into audiology to enhance hearing assessment accuracy, automating hearing devices including cochlear implant (CI), and to promote auditory rehabilitation (Frosolini et al., 2024; Keshavarzi et al., 2018). This could help improving audiologist competencies, individualizing patients care, and minimize routine activities, in addition to enhance the performance of hearing aids to maximize their benefits for individuals with hearing impairments. (Frosolini et al., 2024). On the other hand several challenges may face using AI in audiology, comprising privacy considerations, models biases, the need to validate AI models prior to applying on patients, lack of knowledge and awareness of AI among audiologists, and large requirements of data to train machines (Frosolini et al., 2024).

More recently the term deep learning rises as a type of machine learning that based on using a multiple-layers artificial neural network which allow it to process complex patterns in large datasets, that making deep learning efficient to accomplish tasks related to enhance the output of the hearing aids like noise reduction and speech recognition (Frosolini et al., 2024).

Speech is the corner stone of human communication. According to Yuliani et al. (2021), speech production is the conversion of linguistic structures into acoustic waveforms through complex articulatory mechanisms in the vocal tract to generates sound waves that travel through the air to the listener's auditory system. Then, these received sound waves are encoded by the brain to extract meaningful linguistic information. These processes form the speech chain model, which serves as the foundation for understanding human communication. Environmental noise, reverberation, and various types of acoustic interference frequently distort speech signals, which represent a challenge for hearing-impaired individuals to receive and understand speech.

Speech enhancement technologies in hearing aids have emerged as key solutions to speech problems through improving both the quality and intelligibility of speech signals by reducing noise while preserving the original speech components. Traditional speech enhancement methods, such as spectral subtraction, Wiener filtering, and minimum mean square error (MMSE) estimators often fail in dynamic acoustic environments as noise characteristics change rapidly. The limitations of traditional speech enhancement methods have led to employing deep learning techniques in hearing aids in order to enhancing speech. (Yuliani et al., 2021)

Despite rapid advancements in both artificial intelligence (AI) and auditory assistive technologies, there remains a significant knowledge gap regarding the recent progress and practical implementation of AI methodologies in hearing aid systems. The current literature lacks a systematic synthesis of how these AI techniques have been adopted, optimized, and deployed across different hearing aid platforms over the past decade. As a result, the extent to which AI has transformed real-world hearing aid performance, user experience, and clinical

outcomes remains underexplored and necessitates further investigation.

2. NEED OF THE STUDY

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into hearing aid technology has demonstrated significant potential in enhancing speech clarity, reducing noise, and personalizing user experiences, yet critical gaps persist in understanding its full impact over the past decade (2015–2024). This literature review aims to explore the integration and evolution of AI techniques—including machine learning, deep learning, and neural networks—in hearing aid technology, with a specific focus on their application in speech enhancement and noise reduction. While existing studies highlight these advancements, the literature remains fragmented, lacking a comprehensive synthesis of how artificial intelligence methods have been practically implemented and their real-world efficacy in improving auditory functions, user experience, and rehabilitation efficiency.

Technical challenges such as computational demands, data privacy concerns, and the opaque nature of artificial intelligence decision-making further hinder adoption,

compounded by a shortage of clinical guidelines and training for audiologists. Additionally, despite artificial intelligence's technical benefits, its accessibility for elderly or digitally inexperienced users and its ability to balance speech enhancement with critical environmental sound detection remain understudied, posing safety and usability concerns.

By reviewing AI's evolution in hearing aids, this study not only analyses its transformative potential but also highlights key technical, ethical, and clinical barriers to adoption. Ultimately, it seeks to bridge these gaps by offering actionable recommendations for future research and interdisciplinary collaboration, guiding stakeholders toward optimizing artificial intelligence -driven solutions for diverse user needs.

3. METHODOLOGY:

A thematic analysis approach was employed to structure and synthesize the findings of this literature review. The search strategy involved searching across multiple scientific databases, including Google Scholar, PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Scopus. Relevant publications were identified using a

combination of targeted search terms comprise “artificial intelligence,” “hearing aids,” “machine learning,” “noise reduction,” and “speech enhancement.” The selection of these keywords aimed to capture a comprehensive set of studies addressing the application of artificial intelligence techniques in auditory assistive technologies. Articles published between 2015 and 2024 were considered to ensure the inclusion of the most recent advancements within the field.

3.1 Inclusion criteria

- Peer-reviewed journal articles, conference papers, and review studies published between 2015 and 2024.
- Publications focusing on the application of artificial intelligence techniques—specifically machine learning, deep learning, and neural networks—in hearing aid technology.
- Studies addressing artificial intelligence-driven improvements in speech enhancement, noise reduction, user personalization, or auditory rehabilitation.
- Research available in English.

3.2 Exclusion criteria

- Non-peer-reviewed sources, such as opinion pieces, editorials, or unpublished theses.
- Publications focusing solely on general audiology without artificial intelligence integration.

4. PROCEDURE

A literature search was carried out across multiple scholarly databases, including Google Scholar, PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Scopus, to ensure broad coverage of peer-reviewed publications relevant to the integration of artificial intelligence in hearing aid technologies. The search process employed a predefined set of keywords designed to capture studies focused on speech enhancement, noise reduction, deep learning, and artificial intelligence-assisted hearing devices published between the years 2015 and 2024. During the initial screening phase, titles and abstracts were carefully examined to exclude duplicate entries and studies that were clearly unrelated to the research scope.

Articles deemed potentially relevant underwent full-text review to determine

eligibility based on the established inclusion and exclusion criteria, which considered factors such as publication date, study design, technological focus, and population relevance. Following article selection, pertinent data—including study objectives, methodologies, artificial intelligence techniques used, and key findings—were extracted. A thematic analysis approach was then employed to categorize and synthesize the findings, enabling the identification of dominant research themes, technological advancements, recurring challenges, and existing gaps in the literature. This structured methodology ensured both the rigor and reproducibility of the review process, providing a reliable foundation for drawing meaningful conclusions about the state of artificial intelligence integration in hearing aid technology.

5. Results / Review of Literature

The results of reviewing studies achieved inclusion criteria were classified into Four themes comprise: overview of machine learning as an artificial intelligence type, Applications of artificial intelligence in audiology and hearing aids, benefits and outcomes of applying artificial intelligence

and machine learning in hearing aids, and challenges and limitations. The Table 1 shows search results of each database.

5.1 Theme one: overview of machine learning

Machine learning as a subfield of AI can solve problems by gathering dataset to build a statistical model which may be employed to solve the given problem. It processes inputs and gathered data to learn and improve its performance in solving problems, making decisions, and provide predictions. Despite the intelligence of AI, but the human represents an essential component of the process by feeding machine learning with more datasets and diversity of inputs data during training the model and by increasing used features or parameters to create the desired model. (Balling et al., 2021; Fabry & Bhowmik, 2021).

Machine learning is widely integrated into hearing science, hearing aid devices, speech enhancement, and language fields (AlSamhori et al., 2024; Balling et al., 2021; Keshavarzi et al., 2018). Brain-controlled hearing aids is one of the machine learning applications, it can track brainwaves and

identify the speaker the listener is listening to. Then the hearing aid will amplify the attended sound to particularly facilitate hearing the identified speaker and inhibit others in crowd. This technology is known as auditory attention decoding (AAD). Due to challenges to separate the speaker accurately, neural network models were the focus to enhance identifying of the desired speaker in real time with low-latency speech separation. It simulates the work of biological neurons that making it very effective to be used in machine learning. To reduce technical barriers to employing auditory attention decoding (AAD) in assisting people with hair loss, the recent research focus is to understand auditory attention and related markers in the biological auditory cortex (Umashankar et al., 2021)

Using machine learning AI technologies in hearing aids exceeds detecting particular speaker to provide more intelligent features such language real-time translation, track physical and psychosocial health, and even sense falls, then sending a notification for family members combined with the GPS location. A promise characteristic is that these systems can work on both quiet and

noise to provide optimum speech perception. The rise of Deep Learning technology as a type of machine learning enabled processing complex datasets patterns by using artificial neural networks (Frosolini et al., 2024). It became more popular and employed in hearing aids later after 2019 (Umashankar et al., 2021).

Deep learning is a form of machine learning that uses artificial neural networks (Nahavandi et al., 2022). By developing deep neural networks and a convolution neural network that use multilayers artificial neural networks, machine learning gets the advance to deeply process more complex patterns and datasets (Keshavarzi et al., 2018; Park et al., 2020; Umashankar et al., 2021). Recurrent neural networks, is a type of deep neural networks that provides a superior ability in recognizing speech, language, and time series data processing, which enabled more accurate dealing with such data (Keshavarzi et al., 2018). With more layers of the deep neural networks, the ability to process input information will increase (Park et al., 2020). It simulates the human cerebral cortex, so it can solve problems that were previously dependable only on human intelligence (Fabry & Bhowmik, 2021). Hearing devices

began widely utilising deep neural networks lately in 2019, and it was effective to reduce noise (Umashankar et al., 2021).

There are numerous advantages to integrating machine learning techniques within modern hearing aid technologies. In a comprehensive review of 38 peer-reviewed studies, You et al. (2020) explored the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in otology, with a focus on hearing assistive devices. Their findings indicate that machine learning -enabled hearing aids possess the ability to automatically predict and adjust user-specific settings based on auditory environments and individual hearing profiles. This adaptive personalization enhances the listening experience by improving speech intelligibility and reducing the need for manual configuration. As a result, users can interact with their devices more intuitively, leading to increased autonomy and reduced reliance on audiologists for routine adjustments.

The study by You et al. (2020), also found that beyond acoustic optimization, the integration of AI extends the functionality of hearing aids into broader health and communication domains. For instance, some advanced devices now offer real-time

language translation, supporting cross-linguistic communication, which is particularly beneficial in multilingual settings. Additionally, these systems are capable of continuously monitoring the user's auditory status and physical activity, contributing to long-term health tracking and early detection of anomalies. Such features not only align hearing aids with the growing field of digital health but also promote preventive care by enabling remote monitoring and data sharing with healthcare providers.

5.2 Theme two: Applications of Artificial intelligence (AI) in audiology and hearing aids:

There are various applications of AI and machine learning in audiology. These comprise counselling systems and peer support for patients with chronic audiological illness, predicting of hearing problems to provide prevention and early diagnosis, improve sensors of hearing aids, and therapy and rehabilitation. In a recent scoping review conducted by Frosolini et al. (2024) included 104 articles to explore the applications of and challenges to employing artificial intelligence into audiological practices. Results shows that most of AI

applications on audiology focus on therapeutic and prognostic tools that aims to enhance patient's treatment and predict their outcomes (34.6%) and on hearing testing (33.7%). Similarly, a literature review by Hohmann (2023) reported many applications for machine learning in hearing aids that included employing artificial intelligence in improving signal enhancement to reduce noise, virtualizing real hearing process, and connecting hearing aids to smart phones applications. One more literature review by AlSamhori et al. (2024) reported multi applications for machine learning in audiology, these includes adding artificial intelligence to hearing assessment tools to collect and process data, employing machine learning in diagnosing hearing problems, and personalised audiological rehabilitation for patients with hearing loss.

In a short review conducted by Umashankar et al. (2021), many applications for machine learning in hearing aids were viewed, it is called Auditory Attention Decoding (AAD), these includes brain-controlled hearing aids in which the AI will recognise the brain wave and follow the desired sound the individual is listening to then amplify it to make the focus on this sound. Another application is

the direct translation on real time; the AI will receive the sound and translate it to the desired language in real time. An example of such technologies is the Widex AI that based on "Sound Sense Learn", this feature can help the user personalizing the hearing aid setting and control the suitable listening environment, the Widex Evoke program, called "Sound Sense Adapt" is an application of this technology. Many hearing devices employed AI to add more features including falling detection, tracking footsteps, and activity levels. The review also provides an overview of using machine learning in cochlear implants which enabled processing sounds, reduce noises, process music, and enhance speech.

Smart Speech Enhancement (SSE) systems is another important application of machine learning in hearing aids, it can distinguish between ordinary background noise and important environmental sounds like emergency alarms, approaching vehicles, and other critical sounds (Nossier et al., 2023).

5.3 Theme three: Outcomes of applying machine learning in Hearing aids

Some of the main outcomes and benefits of employing machine learning AI technologies in hearing aids are related to either noise reduction and/or speech enhancement.

5.3.1 Noise reduction: the role of machine learning and AI technologies

People with impaired hearing face the problem of noise that reduce their abilities to hear clearly when using hearing devices. Although the classical hearing aids able to reduce some of these noises, but it still not enough to completely reduce the environmental noise, this simply related to the need to reduce each kind of noise, which is difficult to be achieved with traditional hearing devices (Park et al., 2020). This problem originates from the techniques commonly used to reduce noise, which depend on compensation based on sound frequencies that amplify soft sounds but not louds ones, so the patient can hear with less noise (Andersen et al., 2021).

Based on Andersen et al. (2021) overview of typical hearing aids noise reduction, sounds have to go through multi-phases to filter

environmental noises. These include converting input sounds from two or more microphones to a time and frequency data using analysis filter banks, then the beamforming process controls which of them should be delayed then combined them together using a pre-programmed algorithm. In the postfiltering process there will be suppression of any noise that was not filtered by beamforming and this bases on both time and frequencies of the input sound, at the end there is a process called synthesis filter bank that convert the sound's time and frequency again to sounds. While this technique can reduce noise for sounds with various frequencies, but this will not be effective if input sounds frequencies were highly correlated as it will not be a simple algorithm to process, as a result, the patient will complaint that the noise still disturbs their hearing process.

Machine learning, and especially deep learning techniques were introduced to hearing aids as a promising solution in improving noise reduction. This could be due to using convolution neural network - a special type of neural networks- to reduce environmental noise by converting the sound signals to images, then using filters and

sharpening masks to reduce noises (Park et al., 2020). The article by Andersen et al. (2021) states that deep learning can replace the typical use of specific algorithm by a flexibly generating algorithms based on training on how to reduce noises, then the neural networks will be trained to work as a postfilter, which can produce a sharper sound to make it more speech-like. The study discussed several experiments results to show the benefits of noise reduction and concluded that using the advanced technologies such deep learning can help to improve signal to noise ratio, reduce listening efforts, and help patients to focus better.

Reducing wind noise represents one of the most critical needs for hearing aid users. Unlike electronic or environmental noise, wind creates turbulent airflow around hearing aid microphones, generating random pressure fluctuations that are perceived as loud, low-frequency noise. Traditional approaches to wind noise reduction have focused on both physical (microphone designs, protective covers, and strategic placement of microphones) and algorithmic solutions (high-pass filtering). However, these approaches have significant limitations

comprise removing low-frequency speech components that are important for intelligibility and sound quality, not addressing the non-linear distortions caused by microphone saturation in strong winds and failing to account for the time-varying nature of wind noise. Recent advances in machine learning, particularly using recurrent neural networks, have shown promise in addressing these limitations. Recurrent neural networks are particularly suited to wind noise reduction because they can model temporal dependencies in the signal, allowing them to distinguish between wind noise patterns and speech patterns that evolve over time. (Keshavarzi et al., 2018)

In an experimental study was conducted by Keshavarzi et al. (2018) among 18 participants to assess benefits of employing a specific type of deep neural networks (recurrent neural network) to reduce wind noise. Results shows that deep learning technologies are possibly effective to reduce wind noise when added to hearing aids.

5.3.2 Speech Enhancement in hearing aids: the role of machine learning AI technologies

Unlike conventional approaches that rely on rigid mathematical models, deep learning-based speech enhancement systems learn

directly from data, allowing them to adapt to various noise conditions more effectively. Results of the study conducted by Yuliani et al. (2021) reported a significant improvements in speech enhancement performance, with modern systems achieving 3-5 dB higher SNR improvements than traditional methods in challenging conditions. Furthermore, subjective listening tests have demonstrated substantial gains in both speech quality and intelligibility - metrics that are particularly important for hearing-impaired individuals

Deep neural networks have demonstrated success in speech enhancement tasks. It might be trained to estimate a time-frequency mask that, when applied to the noisy input, suppresses noise components while preserving speech components. The ideal ratio mask (IRM) has emerged as a particularly effective target for such networks, as it provides a soft decision about how much each time-frequency component should be attenuated. In the study conducted by Zhao et al. (2018), results show the remarkable effectiveness of these approaches, even in challenging reverberant environments, and also that in studies with hearing-impaired listeners, deep neural

networks -based systems processing speech with reverberation times of 0.6 seconds demonstrated intelligibility improvements that brought hearing impairment listeners' performance close to that of normal-hearing listeners in quiet conditions, which represents a significant breakthrough, as reverberation has traditionally been one of the most difficult challenges for speech enhancement systems.

According to Zhao et al. (2018), the success of deep learning in speech enhancement based on several advantages including systems ability to learn from extremely large datasets and capturing a wide variety of noise types and acoustic conditions, they can model complex and non-linear relationships that traditional linear systems cannot, and they can adapt their processing based on contextual information across both time and frequency.

The integration of artificial intelligence into hearing aids has transformed them from simple amplification devices into sophisticated auditory assistants. Modern AI-powered hearing aids can automatically adapt to different listening environments, learn user preferences, and even anticipate the user's auditory needs. This represents a

significant advancement over traditional hearing aids that required manual adjustments for different situations. The study by Umashankar et al. (2021) highlights the benefit of applying artificial intelligence in hearing aids to recognize and separately process the wearer's own voice. This addresses a common complaint among hearing aid users who often find their own voice sounds unnatural or "hollow" when amplified. By identifying and specially processing the user's voice while maintaining natural processing of external sounds, artificial intelligence can significantly improve user comfort and satisfaction. As reported by Umashankar et al. (2021), the benefits of these AI technologies extend beyond basic speech intelligibility through reducing the cognitive load associated with listening in noise, which may help mitigate the accelerated cognitive decline associated with untreated hearing loss.

Avoiding safety hazards is another benefit of machine learning technologies, as reported by Nossier et al. (2023), employing machine learning in hearing aids can prevent suppression of important non-speech sounds in the environment like emergency alarms,

approaching vehicles, and other critical sounds through what is known as Smart Speech Enhancement (SSE) systems that can identify different types of environmental sounds. When emergency sounds are detected, the system can modify its processing to ensure these sounds remain audible while still enhancing speech. This represents a significant advancement over conventional hearing aids that might treat all non-speech sounds equally as noise to be suppressed.

Enhancing Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) is another benefit of using machine learning AI technologies in hearing aids. Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) is a system designed to automatically detect and recognize speech signals from surrounding sounds, its primary function is to distinguish human speech from background noise, enabling the device to focus on and process speech more effectively. The relationship between speech enhancement and automatic speech recognition (AR) systems is complex and sometimes contradictory, so enhanced speech may not be able always to improve Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) performance. This could relate to that speech enhancement processing can sometimes

introduce artifacts or distortions that increase word error rates (WER) in Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) systems, particularly when processing already-clean speech. (Nossier et al., 2023).

The study by Nossier et al. (2023) reported that intelligent switching mechanisms was developed to bypass enhancement when it's not needed. These systems might use signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) estimates or other quality metrics to determine whether enhancement is likely to help or harm recognition accuracy. Some advanced implementations use a secondary neural network specifically trained to make this decision, potentially considering factors like the current acoustic environment, the Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) system's confidence scores, and historical performance data.

5.4 Theme four: Challenges and limitations

Several challenges and limitations face employing machine learning techniques and deep learning approaches. According to Zhao et al. (2018), deep learning approaches require substantial computational resources

for both training and operation, large amounts of labelled training data, and their "black box" nature can make it difficult to understand why they make particular decisions or how to correct errors. Despite these challenges, the performance advantages of deep learning have made it the dominant approach in modern speech enhancement research and applications.

Other challenges were reported by Umashankar et al. (2021) comprise the requirement to more sophisticated hardware with greater processing power and energy efficiency, they raise privacy concerns particularly when using physiological data like brainwaves, and they create new demands for user education and support as their capabilities and interfaces are more complex than traditional hearing aids. Despite these challenges, the benefits of AI in hearing assistance are driving rapid adoption and continued innovation in the field.

Several technical challenges to the implementation of Smart Speech Enhancement (SSE) were reported by Nossier et al. (2023), First, the sound classification system must be highly accurate to avoid false alarms or missed detections.

Second, the enhancement processing must be flexible enough to handle both speech and emergency sounds appropriately. Third, the entire system must operate with minimal latency to ensure timely awareness of important sounds. Current approaches often use multi-task learning frameworks where a single neural network performs both classification and enhancement, though some systems use separate specialized networks for each function.

Clinical evaluations of Smart Speech Enhancement (SSE) systems have shown promising results. Users report greater confidence in their ability to hear important environmental sounds while still benefiting from speech enhancement in noisy situations. However, challenges remain in handling highly complex acoustic environments where multiple sound sources overlap, and in maintaining performance across diverse emergency sound types that may vary by region or context.

Challenges to wind noise reduction using AI techniques include handling extremely strong wind conditions where microphone saturation is unavoidable, maintaining performance across different hearing aid styles and microphone configurations, and

minimizing computational requirements to preserve battery life (Keshavarzi et al., 2018).

Nossier et al. (2023) reported that future directions in Smart Speech Enhancement (SSE) research include the integration of visual cues (through cameras or augmented reality displays) to provide additional context about sound sources, and the development of more sophisticated decision algorithms that can prioritize different sounds based on situational importance. These advancements promise to make hearing aids not just communication devices, but comprehensive environmental awareness tools.

Regarding wind noise reduction, the study conducted by Keshavarzi et al. (2018), reported that Future solutions may combine physical, algorithmic, and machine learning approaches to provide more comprehensive protection against wind noise in hearing aids. As the integration of speech enhancement with Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) become more sophisticated, with capabilities like real-time captioning or language translation, the need for enhancement that's optimized for machine listening rather than human listening will continue to grow. This

represents an important area for future research at the intersection of speech processing and hearing technology (Nossier et al., 2023).

6. DISCUSSION

The current review highlighted the transformative impact of machine learning and artificial intelligence (AI) technologies on the field of audiology, particularly in the development and enhancement of modern hearing aids. The findings show that machine learning technologies has shifted the paradigm in auditory support systems from passive amplification towards intelligent, responsive, and context-aware devices. This discussion evaluates these findings in relation to the existing body of research, examines the benefits and limitations of AI-enhanced hearing technologies, and identifies opportunities and challenges for future application and research.

Machine learning, as a type of AI, has become central to a variety of fields due to its capacity to analyse massive datasets and adaptively solve complex problems. In audiology, machine learning techniques are being employed to reduce noise, enhance speech, and individualise user experiences

(Balling et al., 2021; Fabry & Bhowmik, 2021). The snowballing application of deep learning techniques qualified hearing aids to detect, distinguish, and prioritise relevant auditory inputs more effectively than ever before (Keshavarzi et al., 2018; Park et al., 2020; Umashankar et al., 2021). Such progresses imply not only technological advancement, but it redefines abilities of hearing aids. Though promising, AI applications in hearing aids comprise various and technical challenges, particularly concerning user privacy and data security, due to the physiological nature of the input data and the demand to high computational power and sophisticated real-time processing which raise concerns about battery life and hardware feasibility in compact hearing aid designs (Umashankar et al., 2021). This may direct future researches toward expanding the field to overcome these ethical and technical challenges by collaborate with other disciplines.

The findings also underline the increasing complexity of AI-powered hearing aids, which introduces new demands in terms of user education and support. Unlike traditional devices that require minimal input, modern AI-driven hearing aids

involve user-specific training, app synchronisation, and adaptive learning processes. As such, users must be equipped with the digital literacy to navigate these features, and audiologists must be trained to interpret and configure machine learning systems appropriately (Umashankar et al., 2021). This is another evidence of the gap in knowledge about digital literacy, principles of education about such advanced technologies, the need to motivate audiologist to engage in learning about this field, and the need to organize conferences and related workshops.

A significant outcome identified in the review concerns noise reduction. The findings clearly show that unlike traditional hearing aids, machine learning models offer dynamic, context-sensitive solutions. Convolution neural network, for example, process sound waves by converting them into spectrogram-like representations, enabling the device to filter out noise using visual pattern recognition techniques (Park et al., 2020). Moreover, recurrent neural networks have been utilised to distinguish between environment noises (e.g. wind noise) and consistent speech patterns. These capabilities are promising to overcome one

of the most intrusive challenges facing hearing aids to reduce wind noise, so future solutions may combine physical, algorithmic, and machine learning approaches to provide more comprehensive protection against wind noise in hearing aids (Keshavarzi et al., 2018).

Speech enhancement is another outcome for integrating machine learning in hearing aids. The findings of this review show that unlike traditional speech enhancement techniques, deep learning models can allow datasets to adapt to real-world variations in the mean of speech and environmental noise which can significantly narrow the gap in comprehension between hearing aids users and people with normal hearing (Zhao et al., 2018). Although the results show that the available application of AI in hearing aids looked promising, but there are several limitations were explored. It refers to datasets availability and processing, these comprise the need for extensive and labelled datasets for effective training and the mistrust results from the difficulty to understand or verify the system decisions (Zhao et al., 2018). This can highlight the gap in literature on testing and improving these techniques to eliminate such

limitations and challenges and may direct future researches of the field toward providing datasets, further understanding and individualising decisions made by such systems.

Today's hearing aids aspire to expand supporting advanced features such as real-time translation, fall detection, physical activity monitoring, and remote health data transmission (AlSamhori et al., 2024; You et al., 2020). The integration of such features to hearing aids conflicts with traditional speech enhancement systems that cannot distinguish between background noise and critical voices like alarms and vehicles warning horns. This motivated the evolution of Smart Speech Enhancement (SSE) technologies, which can differentiate between benign background noise and critical auditory cues (Nossier et al., 2023). This represents a significant advance in user safety, particularly for vulnerable populations such as the elderly. But there are many challenges relate to technical and usability, for example, the imbalance between speech enhancement and recognition accuracy that may face Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) systems integrated into hearing aids. While there is a study suggested to overcome this

challenge through intelligent switching systems (Nossier et al., 2023), however, there is a growing need for adaptable, hybrid systems that combine speech enhancement with machine listening optimisation. Since the integration of speech enhancement with Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) become more sophisticated, with capabilities like real-time captioning or language translation, the need for enhancement that's optimized for machine listening rather than human listening will continue to grow. Looking ahead, future research directions are poised to enhance both the technical sophistication and practical utility of AI-enhanced hearing aids. Nossier et al. (2023) reported that future directions in Smart Speech Enhancement (SSE) research include the integration of visual cues (through cameras or augmented reality displays) to provide additional context about sound sources, and the development of more sophisticated decision algorithms that can prioritize different sounds based on situational importance. These advancements promise to make hearing aids not just communication devices, but comprehensive environmental awareness tools.

7. Conclusion

Machine learning AI technologies offer significant opportunities for improving the functionality, adaptability, and user experience of hearing aids. While current advancements have delivered substantial gains in speech enhancement and noise reduction, a range of technical, ethical, and practical challenges must be addressed to maximise the clinical and societal impact of these technologies. The field stands at a critical juncture where interdisciplinary collaboration—across audiology, computer science, and ethics—is essential to guide the future development of intelligent hearing solutions. Although testing applications of machine learning techniques in hearing aids are expanding, but the findings of this review indicate scarcity of studies in this field. The dominant focus of the literature was on reviewing available studies rather than testing and validating applications of machine learning techniques in hearing aids.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS:

Based on the findings of this literature review, several points can be recommended to guide future research, development, and clinical implementation of machine learning

and artificial intelligence (AI) technologies in hearing aids:

For practice:

- **Enhance Digital Literacy and provide Professional Training:** there is a need to enhance digital literacy among hearing aid users to ensure effective use of AI-enhanced devices. It is highly recommended to develop well understood user guides to support users' engagement with these advanced technologies.
- **Establish ethical considerations:** there is a high demand to develop a code of ethics for using AI-enhanced hearing aids. This include providing a guideline concerning data privacy, informed consent, and the safe use of AI assistive technologies.
- **Improve Explainability and Transparency:** AI-enhanced hearing aids should be provided by advanced datasets and frameworks that enable both audiologist and hearing aids users to understand and trust decision-making processes, thereby increasing adoption and confidence.

For researchers:

- Focus on Real-World Testing and Validation: it is a message for researchers in the field to conduct further researches that test and validate using of AI technologies in hearing aids.
- Expand and share Datasets: there is a high demand to develop needed datasets to train AI-enhanced hearing aids, and it's highly recommended to share such datasets and collaborate to improve it.
- Enhance Interdisciplinary Collaboration: encourage collaboration between audiologist, engineers, computer scientist, and ethical specialists to face all possible challenges and limitations in employing AI into hearing aids.

For education:

- Enhance Digital Literacy and Professional Training: it's highly needed to provide continuing education and training for audiologists on AI-based hearing aid systems and to include AI and machine learning modules in audiology curricula.
- Facilitate ongoing education about the role of AI in audiology through conferences, workshops, and seminars.

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Table 1.

Search results

Database	Search keywords	Results before filtering	Filters	results	After title and abstract	selected
PubMed	(artificial intelligence) AND (hearing aids) AND (machine learning) AND (noise reduction) AND (speech enhancement)	7	Years 2015-2024	6	4	2
ScienceDirect	artificial intelligence AND hearing aids AND machine learning AND noise reduction AND speech enhancement	246	Years 2015-2024	137	15	6
SCOPUS	artificial AND intelligence AND hearing AND aids AND machine AND learning AND noise AND reduction AND speech AND enhancement	243	Years 2015-2024	203	21	8
Google Scholar	artificial AND intelligence AND hearing AND aids AND machine AND learning AND noise AND reduction AND speech AND enhancement	-	Years 2015-2024	-	23	10